

DIGITALIZATION OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION AND VARIOUS SPHERES OF SOCIETY: SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL APPROACHES

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Abstract. This article analyzes the concept of “digitalization” by the author, its impact on public administration and various sectors of society, the role of the digitalization process in improving the efficiency of public administration. Also, as a result of comparative analysis of the views of scholars and legal norms, the interpretation, goals and objectives of digitalization in various fields have been developed.

Key words: public administration, society, digitalization, digital technologies, e-government.

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада “рақамлаштириш” тушунчаси, унинг давлат бошқаруви ва жамиятнинг турли соҳаларига таъсири, давлат бошқаруви самарадорлигини оширишда рақамлаштириш жараёнининг туган ўрни таҳлил қилинган. Шунингдек, олимларнинг назарий ёндашувлари ҳамда амалдаги қонунчилик нормаларини қиёсий таҳлил қилиш орқали турли соҳаларда рақамлаштиришдан фойдаланиш, бундан кўзланган мақсад ва истиқболдаги вазифалар тўғрисида хулоса чиқарилган.

Калит сўзлар: давлат бошқаруви, жамият, рақамлаштириш, рақамли технологиялар, электрон ҳукумат.

Аннотация. В статье анализируется понятие «цифровизация», его влияние на государственное управление и различные сферы общества, роль процесса цифровизации в повышении эффективности государственного управления. В результате сравнительного анализа мнений ученых и содержания правовых норм выработано толкование и сформулированы цели и задачи цифровизации в различных сферах.

Ключевые слова: государственное управление, общество, цифровизация, цифровые технологии, электронное правительство.

During the computer revolution of the twentieth century, the process of transition from analog methods of data processing to the digital standard took place, and their use led to a radical change in the entire technological environment. Digitalization, the essence of technical means as a starting point for

understanding digital technology terms, and the content of the technologies that form the basis of these processes can be pointed out.

Looking at recent history, it can be said that the introduction of mechanical devices and aggregates, the widespread introduction of mechanization pro-

cesses, as well as electronic computers and the introduction of automated control systems in some sectors of the economy, enterprises and organizations in many respects were the basis of modern change.

The development of computer technology and the creation of the Internet have led to the emergence of information and communication technologies, and consequently, the beginning of the informatization process. It can be said that this process is not only the initial stage of digitalization, but also an integral part of it, because the information industry and information technology are inextricably linked with the digital industry and digital technologies.

The proliferation of the type of robots associated with the interaction of artificial intelligence and neural networks should also be seen as digital technology. In this regard, it is possible to put forward the logical conclusion of S.M.Zubarev that "... robotization should be recognized as an aspect of digitalization"¹.

Recently, the term "digitalization" is increasingly used in political, legal and regulatory documents, as well as in scientific research. Unfortunately, there is no legal interpretation of the concept of digitalization in official sources, and only there exists a general understanding of it in the scientific community.

In most cases, scientists use this term, which describes² the modern conditions of social development, without disclosing its meaning, some use the terms "digitalization" and "informatization" as synonyms³, while others distinguish "digitalization" from "informatization" and "robotization"⁴.

However, the concept of "digitalization" does not yet have a clear scientific interpretation. This situation forces us to turn to the analysis of approaches to the digitalization of society formed in social knowledge.

It can be observed that the concept of "digitalization" is now used in a narrow and broad sense in the scientific literature. In the narrow sense, it is general-

ly understood the process of converting information used to reduce costs (e.g., to store it) and new information into a special digital form. In a broad sense, digitalization is seen as an effective way to digitize data that meets certain requirements.

Digital transformation involves not only the transfer of data from analog media (text, audio, video) to digital format, but also the creation of a new product in digital form⁵.

The introduction of digital technologies shows that digital operations are less costly than direct and paper operations, but this method can only be effective if it is used in all areas of public administration. All levels are fully covered and successfully implemented when focused on digital change.

The main condition for successful digitalization is manifested in the revision of all processes based on the complete elimination of traditional "paper" processes and any face-to-face interactions. The main task of digital transformation, including data, services and general infrastructure, is to maximize the benefits for consumers (users, citizens), to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of government agencies.

The concept of digitalization is interpreted by the technical community as a systematic approach to the use of digital resources to increase labor productivity, increase competitiveness and achieve real economic benefits. According to them, in the technical sense, digitalization is the transfer of information from analog to digital form. This not only increases the size and speed of the data being transmitted, but also allows the data to be transmitted and repeated with absolute accuracy without distortion.

The social sciences, on the other hand, define digitalization as a new stage in the industrial revolution, a form of modernization that gives society a new set of tools and technologies that enable it to apply a new type of social communication on a larger scale.

¹ Зубарев С.М., Правовые риски цифровизации государственного управления. //Актуальные проблемы российского права. – 2020 – Т. 15. - № 6. – С. 25. – DOI. 10.17803/1994-1471.2020.115.6.023-032.

² Арабян М. С., Гильманова К. М. Цифровизация как приоритетный инструмент совершенствования таможенного администрирования на примере ЕАЭС // Таможенное дело. 2019. № 4. С. 17—21; Ищенко П. П. Современные подходы к цифровизации досудебного производства по уголовным делам // Lex russica. 2019. № 12. С. 68—79; Ягофарова И. Д. Теоретико-методологические подходы к правовому обеспечению трансформации агропромышленного комплекса в условиях цифровизации // Государственная власть и местное самоуправление. 2019. № 11. С. 11—15.

³ Липень С. В. Законы о нормативных правовых актах стран СНГ — индикаторы процессов информатизации и цифровизации системы законодательства // Актуальные проблемы российского права. 2019. № 8. С. 22—33.

⁴ Юридическая концепция роботизации : монография / Н. В. Антонова, С. Б. Бальхаева, Ж. А. Гаунова [и др.] ; отв. ред. Ю. А. Тихомиров, С. Б. Нанба. М. : Проспект, 2019. С. 10.

⁵ Масловская Т. С. Цифровая сфера и конституционное право: грани взаимодействия // Конституционное и муниципальное право. 2019. № 9. С. 18—22.

If we turn our attention to the process of digitalization of the economic sphere of society, this aspect of the problem of digitalization is studied by N.Yu. Guryanov, E.A. Istomina, M.L.Kalujskiy, T.N.Shown and in the works of Yudina⁶ etc. The authors link the beginning of the digitalization of the economy with a new level and development of information technology and their widespread introduction into economic processes. In this sense, the digital economy can be called “the communication environment of economic activity on the Internet, as well as the forms, methods, tools and results of its implementation”⁷.

According to scientists, the introduction of information and communication technologies is radically changing the ways of organizing business and managing economic processes. Digitalization, which is the result of a high level of informatization of society, creates new technological opportunities for further development of the world economy. Researchers, therefore, argue that digitalization has a profound impact on global trade and investment, and is capable of transforming economic sectors and industries around the world.

Clearly, in modern society, the concept of “digital economy” is now seen not only as a purely theoretical concept, but also as a separate form that manifests itself in the emergence of electronic payments, e-commerce, online banking and other information services.

E-commerce, smart contracts, blockchain, cryptocurrencies, artificial intelligence - these are all components of digital technology that has already become a reality today. At present, both in the economic and other spheres of society and state life, along with these technologies, digital technological (online) platforms, big data, augmented and virtual reality, robotization of certain processes and professions, etc. are being developed.

The creation and widespread use of digital technologies can be seen as a process of revolutionary

change in modern society – a digital revolution that consistently shapes a new social, economic, political and legal reality.

Digital transformation is a tool to improve the quality of human life in society through the introduction of digital technology. Digital transformation can be applied through the digitalization of public administration, including at the stages of individual parts of public administration, the management cycle, public functions and their types.

This, of course, should lead to an increase in the quality of public administration (efficiency, effectiveness, validity). It should be borne in mind that digitalization can be used only if it serves to improve the quality of life of population and to facilitate the work of civil servants working in the field of public administration.

Of course, in this case, it is advisable to carry out a complete reengineering of the area or process to which digitalization is applied. Otherwise, digitalization can further complicate the existing process. While we are currently working on the development of e-government, subsequent forms of government are evolving⁸.

Implementing digital government, Gartner proposes the concept of digitalization of public administration, first of all, the transition to open government with the development of e-government, then to the data center government, then to digital government and then to the “Smart Government”⁹.

This means that as technology develops, public services need to be improved. Simply put, reducing the number of public services, of course, at the expense of automation and optimization, that is, they do not require a citizen to apply. Thus, in the provision of public services without the participation of the applicant should be the provision of public services based on the rules of life (age, duration, etc.).

As the President Sh.M.Mirziyoev rightly noted, “Digital technologies not only improve the quality of products and services, reduce unnecessary costs.

⁶ Гурьянов Н.Ю., Гурьянова А. В. Цифровая глобализация в контексте развития цифровой экономики и цифровых технологий // Вестник Московского государственного областного ун-та. Философские науки. 2020. № 3. С. 63–69.; Истомина Е.А. Оценка трендов цифровизации в промышленности // Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. – 2018. №12 (422). Экономические науки. Вып.63. С.108-116.; Калужский М. Л. Маркетинговые сети в электронной коммерции: институциональный подход. М.; Берлин: ДиректМедиа, 2014. 402 с; Юдина Т.Н. Цифровизация как тенденция современного развития экономики Российской Федерации: Про у contra // Государственное и муниципальное управление. Ученые записки СКАГС. 2017. № 3. С.139-143.

⁷ Калужский М. Л. Маркетинговые сети в электронной коммерции: институциональный подход. М.; Берлин: ДиректМедиа, 2014. С.151.

⁸ Рахманов Қ.С. Давлат бошқарувида рақамлаштиришдаги муаммо ва ечимлар // “Давлат бошқарувида рақамлаштириш: муаммо ва ечимлар” мавзuida Республика илмий-амалий конференцияси материаллари. – Т.: Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти ҳузуридаги Давлат бошқаруви академияси, 2019. – 86-б.

⁹ Gartner. 5 Levels of Digital Government Maturity. November 6, 2017. Available at: <https://www.gartner.com/smarterwithgartner/5-levelsofdigital-government-maturity>.

At the same time, they are an effective tool in overcoming the most serious scourge – the scourge of corruption”¹⁰. In developed countries, digitalization is emerging as the basis for the formation of the transition to a digital economy and its “effective development trend”.

“With the rapid development of information and communication technologies (ICT) and the beginning of the active informatization process resulting from the formation of the technological order, the need for a new term arose spontaneously”.

According to V.G.Khalin, G.V.Chernova, “Digitalization is a major modern trend in the development of the economy and society based on the transition to a digital format of information presentation, which is characterized by its focus on improving economic efficiency and quality of life”¹¹.

From this it can be said that the economy was one of the first to feel the impact of digitalization. It should be noted that the American economist Nicholas Negroponte (University of Massachusetts, USA) first used the term “digitalization” in 1995 in the de-

velopment of the concept of e-economy and put it into scientific circulation¹².

Digital technologies are penetrating not only in the economic sphere, but also in the political processes in society. Different aspects of digitalization in the political and legal spheres have done extensively researched by V. Volodenkov, A.A.Kartsxiya, L.V.Smorgunov¹³.

They link the process of digitalization of the political and legal spheres with the widespread introduction of electronic means in the system of public administration, which, in turn, will significantly simplify the relationship between government and society. Indeed, this process will lead to the emergence of new information services that will allow citizens to express their interests, express their opinions and reveal various forms of social activity. The use of new, more efficient ways of organizing political activity in public administration is gradually replacing the old practices of political activity.

The following table summarizes the generalized interpretation of the concept of digitalization within different areas.

Interpretation of the concept of “digitalization” in various fields

No	Sphere	Definition	Possibilities of digitalization by definition
1	Technical sphere	Converting data from analog to digital form	Ability to increase the size and speed of data, transfer and repeat data with absolute accuracy
2	Economic sphere	The main modern trend of economic development, based on the transition to a digital format of information presentation	New technological opportunities for further development of the world economy, increasing the efficiency of the economy and changing the ways of managing economic processes
3	Political sphere	The process of emerging a new information system aimed at simplifying the relationship between government and society	The opportunity for citizens to freely express their interests and opinions, to reveal various forms of social activity
4	Public administration	The process of introducing digital technologies in the activities of government agencies	Opportunity to perform public functions and improve the quality of public services, to ensure effective cooperation between citizens and state
5	Law sphere	The process of using the digital format in the regulation of legal relations between subjects	Opportunity to prevent bureaucratic barriers and corruption, further optimize the legal regulation

* Developed by the author based on the analysis.

So, as we can see in the table, digitalization can be seen as a process of applying digital technologies in different fields, and digital transformation is reflected in the concrete results that arise from their application.

At a time when today’s informatization process covers all spheres of the state and society, we believe that the interpretation and definition of the concepts of “digitalization” and “digital transformation” in the normative legal documents will help to avoid ambiguities in the application of these concepts.

¹⁰ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Олий Мажлисга Мурожаатномаси // 24.01.2020 / <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/3324>.

¹¹ Халин В.Г., Чернова Г.В. Цифровизация и ее влияние на российскую экономику и общество: преимущества, вызовы, угрозы и риски // Управленческое консультирование. 2018. № 10 (118). С. 46-63.

¹² Negroponte N. Being Digital / N. Negroponte. NY: Knopf, 1995. 256 p.

¹³ Володенков С. В. Digital-технологии в системе традиционных институтов власти: политический потенциал и современные вызовы // Вестник Московского государственного областного ун-та. 2018. № 2. С. 39–48; Карцхия А. А. Цифровая трансформация права // Мониторинг правоприменения. 2019. №1 (3 0). С. 25–29; Сморгунов Л. В. Блокчейн как институт процедурной справедливости // Полис. Политические исследования. 2018. № 5. С. 88–99.